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USE OF FOREIGN EXPERIENCES IN THE EDUCATION OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN (EXAMPLE OF FINLAND, KOREA AND GERMANY)

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Abstract. This article details the characteristics, aims, and purposes of the preschool education approaches used in various nations and applies the most suitable ones in Uzbekistan.

Keywords: preschoolers, kindergarten, method, technique, Montessori system, integral education.

Introduction. One of our main responsibilities is to raise the younger generation that has been growing in our nation over the past few years in a healthy and mature manner. We also need to organize an efficient preschool education system that encourages creative thinking and incorporate effective forms and methods into the educational process. Simultaneously, the analysis reveals the need to guarantee that all children receive preschool education, stock organizations with fiction and instructional and methodological materials, draw in qualified pedagogical and managerial staff, and resolve the challenges associated with integrating cutting-edge technologies into the classroom. The educators, stylists, and psychologists working in preschool educational institutions bear a great deal of responsibility for the successful completion of these responsibilities.

In terms of educational reform, Uzbekistan is moving quickly forward. Because raising a harmoniously formed generation would secure Uzbekistan's future growth is the goal of the extensive changes being implemented now. The main component of this educational system was preschool education. Aiming to enhance and modernize Uzbekistan's preschool education system, legislation and decisions have been established and implemented in recent years. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan № PQ 4312 of May 8, 2019 "On approval of the Concept of development of preschool education in the Republic of Uzbekistan"[1] consists, among other things, of defining the priorities and stages of the process as well as encompassing the target tasks of the system's development.

Preschool education systems must continue to grow by organizing international experiences, analyzing their accomplishments, and incorporating developed nations' best practices while maintaining a focus on domestic education. As a result, an analysis of numerous developed foreign nations' best practices was conducted.

Literature analysis. The introduction, literature analysis, research materials and methods, research results, discussion, and conclusion are the five key sections that make up this article. The introduction section highlights the value of preschool education and the usage of contemporary technology in the classroom. The article's structure is briefly explained via the literature analysis. In the section on study materials and methods, we described Uzbekistan's preschool education experience and listed the resources used to compare it to other nations' technological advancements. The research results section lists the technological and methodological parallels and discrepancies between Uzbekistan and

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several other nations, including Germany, Finland, and Korea. In the discussion section, appropriate technology and approaches from Finland, Germany, and Korea that Uzbekistan can incorporate into its educational system were discussed.

Research materials and methods. Preschool education is the smallest and most fundamental component of education, but in recent years, it has gained attention to the point that it is now the subject of public policy. Specifically, to further enhance the preschool education system, fortify the material and technical foundation, broaden the preschool educational institution network, supply qualified teachers, and significantly raise the younger generation's level of readiness for formal education, comprehensive educational, and pedagogical Resolution No. 2707, "On measures to further improve the system of preschool education in 2017-2021," was adopted by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on December 29, 2016, with the aim of providing sufficient circumstances for the development of artistic, physical, and intellectual skills.

As per the resolution, several crucial and pressing assignments have been noted, including a comprehensive examination of the preschool education systems in other nations, their integration into our own, and collaboration. Naturally, this is crucial for the education and parenting of the younger generation, as we think that the thorough examination and application of the educational system in other nations will undoubtedly open the door for the adoption of more cutting-edge and inventive methods.

In light of this, I believe it is advantageous to employ contemporary teaching techniques extensively and to include international best practices into the upbringing of the next generation. The research's objectives are to examine and put into practice the finest pedagogical approaches while also analyzing the intricacies of the preschool education systems in Germany, Finland, and Korea. The research methodology involves a theoretical examination and generalization of a range of academic works, including websites devoted to the study of preschool education from other educational contexts.

Research results. The study's findings indicate certain parallels between the preschool systems in Korea, Finland, Germany, and Uzbekistan. For instance, there are three different kinds of kindergartens in Finland: private, family-based learning at home, and municipal, or common kindergartens. Kindergarten rules in Germany are comparable to those in the Uzbekistan: for example, children participate in morning exercises, eat breakfast, play, stroll, eat lunch, and nap.

However, there are a lot of variations in the preschool education systems of the aforementioned nations, such as the kindergarten admission policy for infants younger than three months old and the reading instruction provided to young children. In the discussion section, we'll examine the strategies these nations' educators can use to attain such outcomes.

Discussions. In Finland, early childhood education is offered to children younger than school age, often starting at around nine months following a period of parental leave. It can be received at the child's home or at a municipal or private daycare facility.

The first week in the garden is a family week. It is acceptable and even encouraged for one of the parents to be with the baby for the first time - especially if the child does not understand a word of what is said to him. Then gradually he is taught to remain without his family.

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On the first day parents are given a questionnaire with questions about the child's needs and desires like "What is the child's most favorite toy?"

Basic principles for raising little Finns:

- There is no such thing as bad weather - just the wrong clothes. They walk always and everywhere, in the rain and in the cold. And in each wing there are drying cabinets, from which dry things are taken out when you come to pick up your child.
- They do not punish. The maximum that can be done with a bully is to isolate him from other children, for example, he will be seated at a different table at lunch or taken from the playground to a room. Gradually everyone becomes bored, and the hysterics without spectators quickly subside.
- Free childhood. Children are introduced to letters and numbers in a playful way, but they are taught to read and count only at school. The main principle is that the child should have a childhood, a lot of fresh air and carefree fun.
- Everybody knows each other. There are two "own" teachers, but they can easily change with colleagues if they need to go away - everyone knows everyone. Children also know other adults and calmly study with them.
- Cuddling is not taboo. The teachers freely carry the children in their arms and hug if the kids need it, calmly change the diaper and wash them.

In Korea, the focus of preschool education is on the infant's early, complete development. Children are taught to write and read in both English and their local tongue beginning at the age of three. Children are studying the fundamentals of maths at the same age. Both music instruction and physical training receive a lot of attention. Additionally, kindergarteners have some homework.

There are classes where students learn science as well. Preschool's primary objective is to increase kids' curiosity and areas of interest.

Korean children begin to learn reading, counting, music, ballet and drawing at the age of 2-3 years. Kindergarten teachers teach Korean and general development classes. Music, English, physical education, ballet, and drawing are taught only by professionals invited from outside. All kindergartens, without exception, regularly organize trips with children to the zoo, museums or sports complexes, as well as on excursions and just walks. The kindergarten teachers are friendly and patient. If they build children, then strictly, but kindly. They don't yell at children. When meeting children, they kiss, hug and show in every possible way that they are glad to see them. At the same time, the children listen to them and stay close during excursions. Teachers regularly undergo advanced training.

Few kindergartens give children complete creative freedom (although this happens occasionally). At the same time, many kindergartens use some Montessori principles: there is an environment, there are mats, you can take a manual, play and put it in place.

German parents begin choosing a kindergarten a year and a half before pregnancy. The Germans are very pragmatic. In most cases, a child is expected and planned. It is at the moment when the decision is made to expand the family that they begin to look for a kindergarten. The main selection criterion is the location as close as possible to the house. If there is a certain priority based on the type of preschool institution or the method of preschool education used, then it is quite possible that you will have to think about moving to

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another area. And moving is not an event of one day or week, or even one month. Therefore, the issue of kindergarten is dealt with in advance.

Methods of preschool education in Germany:

- Regio Emilio education scheme. The kindergarten is perceived as a “city” where everyone has their own functions. Every morning everyone receives certain tasks, and in the evening their completion is checked.

- Integral education. In groups together there are ordinary children and children with special needs or some developmental disabilities.

- Kindergarten on the farm. The format involves the development of a child in conditions close to natural. Children help grow vegetables, plant ornamental plants, and care for pets.

- Kindergarten in the forest or in nature. Another version of the eco-methodology aimed at introducing a child to nature. Children learn to handle forests carefully, spend a lot of time outdoors, and learn basic skills in working with wood and other natural materials.

- Montessori system. The child is taught independence and self-care skills.

- “According to children’s rules.” Under the supervision of a teacher, children themselves can set certain rules in the group and follow them. The technique promotes the development of creative abilities and teaches children to be independent.

Each preschool institution independently chooses the educational method it will use. Parents can only choose a kindergarten that matches their ideas about education.

Conclusion. As a conclusion, we may state that modern preschool education and parenting need for a fresh approach to the educational process. Simultaneously, the organization, analysis, and filtering of the finest practices of established foreign nations must be included into the current national education system. For instance, Japanese educators in Uzbekistan have discovered a technique to preserve the younger Japanese generation in the area of childrearing. Some of our people now gather and give their super-modern children the moving moons that they no longer play with since they are not contemporary.

The over-technocracy of contemporary kid's games is the cause. They are devoid of the charm, emotion, and human soul. This implies that we need to use our country's educational resources wisely. In addition to educational games created using contemporary pedagogical technology, we should not overlook the traditional games passed down from our forefathers. Due to the special characteristics of these months, children develop good traits like closeness, unity, and willpower through specific activities. Of course, this means accounting for the child's age. [p. 9; 634]

As a result, in selecting preschool curriculum, it's important to incorporate international best practices without sacrificing the moral, physical, and occupational education that shapes national identity. Preschool education establishments will engage in healthy competition. The third Renaissance of Uzbekistan will be ushered in by this process, which will also raise a healthy, intelligent, and gifted generation for it.

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